

Managing Editor's Column

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Dear Readers:

After a number of exciting special issues this is again a regular issue with a total of 13 papers, I think a new record! It is evident from all figures (access numbers, impact factor, etc.) that J.UCS is getting more and more recognition. Hence I hope that you will not only enjoy this issue, but you will help J.UCS even further along three important lines: (1) Make sure that you or your colleagues submit high quality papers in any area of computer science to the journal, (2) If you have established your reputation as top notch researcher, and you are not member of the editorial board of J.UCS yet, consider joining it. It is by now a prestigious item on your CV but requires only a tiny amount of your time, like reviewing 1-2 papers a year. If you are interested, do contact me immediately under hmaurer@iicm.edu. (3) Make sure that your university library, your department or you yourself (via some project funds) subscribe to J.UCS. For just US \$ 110,-/€ 110,- per year the journal is then available to everyone on your campus, from student to the vice-president for research! (Note that subscription rates for companies are a bit higher). For details on how to subscribe see http://www.jucs.org/jucs_subscription.html.

Enough for today, happy reading,

Cordially,

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